

Decomposition of Oxy-salts of Nitrogen: Peroxide Theory

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Experimental results of the investigations recorded in literature along with those of the author and his co-workers on the thermal decomposition of hyponitrites, oxyhyponitrites, nitrites and nitrates of metals are found to lead to the view that metal peroxide is a primary product of the decomposition of all these salts and that this is accompanied with nitrogen, nitrous oxide, nitric oxide and nitrogen dioxide, respectively. Experimental support to the view is provided by the discovery, by the author and his co-workers, of the presence of oxygen in the decomposition of hyponitrites first reported in the case of the lead salt¹. Subsequently oxygen is found present in the decomposition of all hyponitrites and oxyhyponitrites investigated; the latter include sodium², potassium, barium³, calcium, strontium, lithium, magnesium, cadmium and lead salts⁴. The presence of oxygen in the decomposition products of nitrites and nitrates is well-known. These observations enable a coherent hypothesis to be construed to explain the formation of the observed products through the intermediate formation and decomposition of the higher oxysalt, or oxysalts, by the action of the metal peroxide on the undecomposed salt.

THE thermal decomposition of several hyponitrites, oxyhyponitrites, nitrites and nitrates has been investigated by Oza and the co-workers among others. A theory of the decomposition of hyponitrites is published⁵. The theory is now being extended to cover all the oxysalts of nitrogen. According to the theory, hyponitrites of metals decomposed in the primary stage into the metal peroxide and nitrogen. The former then oxidized some of the undecomposed hyponitrite present in the system to produce its oxysalt which, under the conditions of the system, decomposed forming nitrous oxide found present in the products. Since the publication of the theory work is done on lithium and thallium(I) hyponitrites^{4c} and on copper (I & II), cadmium^{4b} and magnesium hyponitrites^{4b}. The Cu(I) salt is found to produce pure nitrogen as gaseous product of its slow decomposition in a temperature-controlled system. This is an interesting observation since till now only the anhyd. sodium salt was known^{6,7} to produce pure nitrogen almost quantitatively as $3\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{Na}_2\text{O} + 2\text{NaNO}_2 + 2\text{N}_2 \dots$ (a), if the temperature of decomposition was not high enough for the nitrite formed to decompose⁸; if, however, nitrite decomposed it admitted nitric oxide into the products. Other hyponitrites produce nitrogen and nitrous oxide and at times nitric oxide too. According to the theory the nitrous and nitric oxides are produced in the secondary stage. Reactions leading to the formation of nitrous oxide are I, II and III as

The Cu(II) salt produces nitrous oxide like other hyponitrites. The production of pure nitrogen by

Cu(I) hyponitrite and not by the Cu(II) salt finds explanation in the total instability of Cu(I) peroxide, Cu_2O_2 , produced in the primary stage of decomposition of the former: as it passes instantly into Cu(II)O as $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{CuO}$. So Cu(II) oxyhyponitrite is not produced and nitrous oxide is not formed. Nitric oxide, in addition to nitrous oxide, is produced by hyponitrites of metals whose normal oxides are relatively unstable at the temperature of decomposition, e.g., silver and mercury salts⁹⁻¹³ which give rise to the metal, in place of the oxide, in their thermal decomposition. Nitric oxide is a product of decomposition of nitrites, MNO_2 (or $\text{M}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$) which are the second higher oxidation products of hyponitrites. Silver and mercury peroxides, produced in the primary stage of decomposition of the hyponitrites, oxidise some of the undecomposed hyponitrite beyond the oxyhyponitrite stage, $\text{M}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$, to $\text{M}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ which, at the temperature of the system, decompose to produce nitric oxide^{14,15}. That sodium oxyhyponitrite, $\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$, produces nitrous oxide in its decomposition has been demonstrated by Oza⁵ and later by Oza and Dipali⁹. The results of investigation on the thermal decomposition of several oxyhyponitrites are now available. The lithium, sodium, potassium, calcium, strontium, barium, magnesium, cadmium, thallium(I), lanthanum and lead salts are prepared and decomposed in this laboratory: some of the results are communicated for publication^{2,3} and the rest have appeared in these^{4(a,b,c)}: all these salts are found to produce nitrous oxide in the gas along with some oxygen while nitrite is found present in the residue. The sodium, potassium and barium salts are found to produce not even a trace of nitric oxide^{2,3} as the temperature of decomposition of the nitrites produced in the system, are higher than the temperature of the system. Nitric oxide is produced, however, if the temperature is allowed to run high^(cf-17). The cadmium salt also

produces no nitric oxide under strictly controlled conditions. Nitrous oxide is the major gaseous product of decomposition in the case of these salts. The remaining oxyhyponitrites are found to produce nitric oxide also, along with nitrous oxide, nitrogen and some oxygen. Often nitric oxide is a major gaseous product just as in the case of the hyponitrites, nitrous oxide (not nitrogen) is a major product.

Prior to investigation in this laboratory, Angeli¹⁶ had reported his work on the sodium salt while Naik, Shah and Patel¹⁷ on sodium, potassium, calcium, strontium, barium, cadmium and lead salts. Angeli had represented the decomposition of the sodium salt as $2\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow 2\text{NaNO}_2 + \text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$... (b)—a case of disproportionation—to which the latter investigators¹⁷ had added that the hyponitrite produced in (b) suffered decomposition side by side (producing nitrogen). The latter workers represented the decomposition of the remaining hyponitrites as $\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{MO} + 2\text{NO}$... (c). Oza⁵, and Oza and Dipali² have shown that the sodium salt produced nitrous oxide (major) along with nitrogen but not nitrogen alone reported by Naik *et al.* while the work on the other salts⁴ has shown the presence of nitrous oxide in *all* cases its proportion being very high with Na, K and Ba salts whose nitrites are stable and low, or very low, in the case of salts of metals whose nitrites are unstable (Cd, Mg, Pb). The most striking result, however, of the investigations on the oxysalts is that nitrous oxide is present and that nitric oxide, reported by Naik *et al.*, is absent *in toto* in the products if the temperature of decomposition is not allowed to rise high enough for the nitrite formed to decompose; while the sodium salt, reported to give pure nitrogen, produces nitrous oxide in large amounts. The nitrites of Mg, Cd, Pb are known to decompose at around 200°, the temperature used in the study of the decomposition of these oxysalts; so nitric oxide produced by these is safely attributable to the secondary decomposition of the produced nitrites. Careful work designed to isolate the gaseous products of the decomposition, in stages, as swiftly as formed has confirmed that nitrous oxide is produced first while nitric oxide, whenever formed, is produced subsequently. Thus the reactions occurring in the decomposition of oxyhyponitrites may be represented as in IV, V and VI below :

Oxygen, not reported earlier, is found present in the decomposition of oxyhyponitrites also^{2,3,4}. This would result from the decomposition, in part, of the peroxide produced in the decomposition. Interestingly, like sodium hyponitrite whose decomposition largely approximates to the requirement of eq. (a), the solid residues in the case of Na, K and Ba oxyhyponitrites, whose gaseous products comprise about 90 percent nitrous oxide, also approximate fairly well to the requirement of the eq. $2\text{M}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow 2\text{MNO}_2 + \text{M}_2\text{O} + \text{N}_2\text{O}$ which is the sum of IV and V given above^{2,3}.

Taking nitrite next some considerable work is reported in literature on the thermal decomposition of nitrites. Those investigated by Oza and coworkers are the Na, K, Mg, Hg (I and II), Ag, Ca, Sr, Ba, Li, Cd and Tl(I) salts. Nitric oxide, nitrogen and nitrogen dioxide (i.e., oxygen) are reported as gaseous and nitrate and oxide, or oxide alone, as the solid product(s) of the decomposition. A careful survey of the results shows that nitric oxide, but *not* nitrogen, is invariably present in the thermal decomposition products of *all* the nitrites. The nitrites of Hg (I and II)^{18,19}, Ag²⁰, Cd²¹ and possibly lead²² produce nitric oxide unmixed with even a trace of nitrogen while the rest produce nitric oxide mixed with nitrogen (and of course, oxygen). M. Oswald²³ held the view that nitrites decomposed in the primary stage as $2\text{MNO}_2 \rightarrow \text{M}_2\text{O} + \text{NO} + \text{NO}_2$... (c) and that nitrogen (and nitrate) were formed in the secondary stage. P. C. Ray²⁴ had, however, envisaged the production of metal peroxide and nitric oxide in the primary stage of the decomposition of nitrites in conformity with the view held out in this paper. Oza²⁵ formerly held the view that nitrites decomposed in the primary stage as $2\text{MNO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{M}_2\text{O} + \text{NO} + \text{NO}_2$... (d); this view being based on the observation, supported by that of Ardnt²⁶, that even after prolonged heating the whole of nitrite did not decompose; so it was supposed that the products of the decomposition recombined, in part, to reproduce some nitrite. It may be stated here, in passing, that more recently Tl(I) nitrite is found to decompose out completely²⁷. All these facts seem to fit better with the mechanism envisaged by P. C. Ray stated above. On this view nitrites would decompose in the primary stage as in VII and produce nitrate as in VIII below :

Thus viewed, the mechanism falls in line with that for the hyponitrites and oxyhyponitrites stated in the foregoing text. As already stated, nitric oxide is invariably present in the decomposition products of *all* nitrites. Further, the published data of the work of Oza and the co-workers on some nitrites where the decomposition happened to be run to, or almost to, completion also show that in the case of nitrites which decomposed to give both nitric oxide and nitrogen, the value of the ratio, NO/N, is high at the start of the decomposition, passes through a minimum and again increases, or tends to increase, about the end. Some results illustrating this feature of the decomposition of nitrites are reproduced below—

VALUES OF RATIO NO/N BETWEEN BEGINNING AND END OF A DECOMPOSITION FOR SOME NITRITES

Stage No.	Ratio : NO/N for			
	Mg(NO ₂) ₂	Ca(NO ₂) ₂	Ba(NO ₂) ₂	KNO ₂
1	54.5	44.6	46.1	3.3
2	23.2	37.0	34.1	1.8
3	50.5	25.5	32.9	1.1
4	51.5	42.8	37.1	0.83
5	51.5	42.8	37.1	0.83
6	121.1	50.0	41.6	0.81
7	—	—	49.0	—

On chain mechanism this implies the presence of an unstable intermediate taking part in the reaction. The assumption that the metal peroxide is the unstable intermediate appears thus to be reasonable enough. Nitrogen dioxide is invariably present, also, in the decomposition products; this will be formed from nitric oxide with oxygen from the metal peroxide²⁷. The instantaneous formation of the nitrate witnessed in the case of potassium nitrite²⁸ and barium nitrite²⁹ is readily explained on this view.

Oxynitrites, $M_2N_2O_5$, do not seem to have been isolated. G. Oddo³⁰ has described $H_2N_2O_5$ as nitrosic or nitroso-nitric acid. On the peroxide theory, the salts of this acid, $M_2N_2O_5$, would decompose in the primary stage as $M_2N_2O_5 \rightarrow M_2O_2 + N_2O_3 (= NO + NO_2)$ and produce the metal oxide and nitrogen dioxide and might produce nitrate in the secondary stage.

The nitrates, MNO_3 (or $M_2N_2O_6$) would decompose in the primary stage as

and produce pernitrate in the system thereafter; but pernitrates too, do not seem to have been isolated: so they would produce, at the temperature of the system, the metal oxide, nitrogen dioxide and oxygen. Nitrates of Ba, Mg, Hg(II) and ammonium have been investigated by Oza and co-workers and work on several other nitrates is recorded in literature^{31,32}. Nitrates of Ba, Mg and Hg(II) are found to decompose (overall) as $2MNO_3 (= M_2N_2O_6) \rightarrow M_2O + 2NO_2 + \frac{1}{2}O_2 \dots (e)$ but the ratio, NO_2/O_2 is not found to be constant between the beginning and end of a decomposition as should be the case if metal peroxide intermediate of varying stability was involved. This is observed by Addison and Logan³³ also. Ammonium nitrate³⁴ is shown to dissociate in the primary stage into ammonia and nitric acid and finally pass into nitrous oxide and water at the same time forming some nitric oxide, nitrogen dioxide and nitrogen. Formation of these observed products of ammonium nitrate could be accounted for on the assumption that nitric acid decomposed in the primary stage into hydrogen peroxide and nitrogen dioxide because, in the system containing ammonia, these highly reactive substances would oxidize ammonia to form the observed products. The decomposition of pure nitric acid to form water, oxygen and nitrogen dioxide is reported in literature³⁵. Water and oxygen can result from hydrogen peroxide.

The nitrates of sodium, potassium and barium are reported to decompose in the initial stage to form nitrite and oxygen as $MNO_3 \rightarrow MNO_2 + \frac{1}{2}O_2$. While it is true that oxygen and nitrite are isolated from these nitrates and even the equilibrium $KNO_3 \rightleftharpoons KNO_2 + \frac{1}{2}O_2$, is investigated to evaluate the equilibrium constant, K, it is not improbable that these equilibria are not of normal type³⁶. Lead and charcoal have to be used for the absorption of oxygen from sodium nitrate while abstraction of one more atom from the nitrite formed is also possible

by using sodium amalgam (E. Divers in the preparation of sodium hyponitrite); and it is not altogether unlikely that the nitrite and oxygen formed from the nitrates are secondary products since, at the temperature of decomposition of the nitrate, the nitrite of these metals is relatively stable; so if the primary products of decomposition of the nitrate were the metal peroxide and nitrogen dioxide, the latter will be in equilibrium with the products of its dissociation²⁷ as $NO_2 \rightleftharpoons NO + \frac{1}{2}O_2$ in the temperature range 140° to 620° ; hence in the case of Na, K and Ba nitrates, nitric oxide will react with the metal peroxide to form nitrite³⁷ leaving oxygen of nitrogen dioxide free. The quantitative formation of sodium nitrite in the abrupt thermal decomposition of sodium hyponitrite⁷ is a case in point. The structure of most of the nitrates is similar³⁸. In the resonance hybrid structure of ionic nitrates two O-atoms are linked to nitrogen differently from the third and the nitrate groups linked to bi- and multi-valent elements are different types³⁸. Thus there are good reasons to suppose that the formation of nitrite and oxygen in the decomposition of nitrates may have a different mechanism than the one presumed. Likewise, the argument that the ultra-violet absorption spectra of sodium nitrate shows bands of nitric oxide, $NO(g)$,³⁸ is also not tenable since this is the case at 700° when the dissociation of nitrogen dioxide is complete in the forward direction (at 620°)²⁷ and so nitrogen dioxide will be absent in the products. As a matter of fact nitrogen dioxide is reported preferentially given off at the start and at the end of the decomposition of praseodimium nitrate³⁹ while $PrNO_4$, identified as an intermediate, is shown to have a partially nitrate structure and may be $PrONO_3$ formed as $Pr(NO_3)_3 \rightarrow PrO_2NO_3 + 2NO_2 \rightarrow PrONO_3 + 2NO_2 + \frac{1}{2}O_2$. Mercury(II) nitrate, $Hg(NO_3)_2$, is reported to pass through $HgONO_3$, presumably as $Hg(NO_3)_2 \rightarrow HgONO_3 + NO_2$ before passing into $Hg(II)O$ ^{31,40}; while manganese nitrate is shown to decompose as $Mn(NO_3)_2 \rightarrow MnO_2 + 2NO_2$.³³ That the solid residue of the decomposition of nitrates contains metal peroxide has also got experimental support. Praseodimium, the ultimate decomposition product of praseodimium nitrate,³⁹ is studied by several investigators⁴¹ and is found to have several intermediate states, PrO_x , in which 'x' varies about 1.5 having a maximum value of 1.822 at 385° . It is also shown that the oxidation state of praseodimium varies from Pr(III) to Pr(IV)⁴². Likewise lead oxide formed from lead nitrate is PbO_x in which 'x' varies between 1.00 and 1.50.

To conclude, the formation of nitrogen, nitrous oxide, nitric oxide and nitrogen dioxide, respectively, from the hyponitrite, oxyhyponitrite, nitrite and nitrate in the primary stage of decomposition has substantial experimental evidence. The presence of nitrite/nitrate in the solid products, witnessed, is also readily explicable on the peroxide hypothesis. The assumption of the transitory existence of the metal peroxide is also not without experimental support as the presence of oxygen in the gaseous decomposition products of hyponitrites and oxyhyponitrites is demonstrated experimentally. The presence of oxygen in the decomposition products of

nitrites and nitrates is not controversial. Finally, such a picture of the decomposition of these salts is in line with our views of the constitution of the oxyacids of nitrogen.

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